

Employee Competencies Interrelation of Workforce Agility Attributes

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ABSTRACT- Organizations must be able to evaluate the performance of their digital efforts quickly to know where to channel human resources and when to pull the plug if necessary. In a demand-based banking services environment the organization need to build agility and competencies to adapt to shift and act on it with speed. The workforce sharpens the behavioral competencies to meet the agility dimensions is an answerable to stay strong in business operations. This research is to understand the relationship of behavioral competencies and workforce agility attributes. It gives the insight of knowledge on employee behavior at workplace to find out the research model. Further, empirical results significant that behavioral competencies of motivation, commitment, analytical reasoning and employee foresight were found to be strongly associated with workforce agility attributes of adaptability, developmental and competent. Moreover, the paper opens up discussion for a strategic managerial implication.

KEYWORDS- Employee Competencies, Workforce Agility, Motivation, Adaptability, Developmental

I. INTRODUCTION

There is a growing understanding about the importance of the fact that competency development and management are critical instruments to boost competitiveness for organizations. The dynamic core competencies of an organization are defined as a set of problem-defining and problem-solving insights, and that these insights, which are developed from organizational learning, foster the strategic growth of an organization [1].

The competencies are now commonly conceptualized as measurable patterns of knowledge, skills, abilities, behaviors, and other characteristics (KSAs) that differentiate high from average performance [2]. Competencies in organizations can be classified as either employee-level or organizational-level [3]. Furthermore, organizational-level competencies are embedded in the employee-level competencies, and the employee level competencies can be further divided into technical competencies and behavioral competencies. The technical competencies are job-related skills and knowledge,

while the behavioral competencies refer to personal attributes or characteristics.

The employee competencies-behavioral and agility of the workforce are integrated, it influences on performance of the employee at the end. These researches pave a unique track to evolve the gaps and relationship of organizational practices, behavioral competencies-agility lead performance implicate for better business sustenance. In current scenario of business banking in India under enormous changes, considered to be the lifeline of the economy and the third largest in the world by 2025. The banks are essentially catalytic in activating technologically advanced, transparent and efficient quality banking system is a need of the hour. Strategic human resources and workforce agile practices are imperative to focus.

A. Research Aim

The purpose of this study is to gain a better understanding of employee behavioral competencies influence on workforce agility, its determinants, interventions in the banking organizations face, when developing it.

B. Statement of the Problem

The success and the failure of the organization depends upon the human resource practices, competencies of the human workforce. The 85% of the employee behavior is rooted with the work how he engaged. The organizations are to be sustain in competition the agility is the sense of strategy. Organizational agility is not into force of action without workforce agility. The workforce inner drive is the behavior what they exhibit connected to the performance of an individual and the organization. The problem of the managerial staff is not able to detect the competencies of behavior of the employees and aligned with the organizational goals appropriately. Until or unless the alignment and detection of the behavioral gaps is not strategic the performance of the organization is in question mark. In a banking service environment employee behavior, agility relationship is a mere significant to study and strategic to understand for apt outcomes.

C. Objective of the Study

To establish the relationship among the, behavioral competencies and agility attributes of the employee to interpret the results for managerial implications for further research.

D. Review of Literature

Competencies involve the collection of success factors necessary to achieve a key result in a particular job or in a particular organizational role. It has to do with intellectual, business, social and emotional abilities. People are rewarded for their abilities and this is influenced by some personal histories [4,5].

Although the meaning and definition of the term "competence" is still controversial[6], for the purposes of our study the definition proposed by Bartram, Robertson, and Callinan adopted [5,7]. A competency is a set of actions that help deliver a desired result or outcomes. Competencies conceptualized in this way are things that people can actually do and observe [8]. Competencies are the ability to apply or use knowledge, skills, abilities, behaviors, and personal characteristics to successfully perform an important work task, a specific function, or a specific role or position. Competencies are, therefore, underlying traits of people that exhibit behaviors and ways of thinking that are generalized in many contexts and persist over time.

E. Components of Competency

Competence has five main components [9]. One is knowledge refers to information and learning that exists within banking employees on financial instruments. Second is skill or ability of an employees to perform a particular task. Third is self-confidence, which is an employee's belief that they can succeed in certain situations, to perform complex tasks. Fourth is traits relate to physical characteristics and consistent reactions to situations or information. Good eyesight is a necessary trait for an employee, as is the ability to stay calm under stress, as well as self-discipline. Fifth is motivation, which is the emotion, desire, physiological need, or similar drive that prompts action. Motives and traits can be said to be the initiators of what people do in the workplace without close supervision. As shown in Figure 1, significant behavior results in improved performance. Proficiency (low, medium, high) is always determined by knowledge, ability, and attitude.

F. Classification of Competencies

The focus of this research is on the behavioral competencies. Prior to application of the behavioral competencies, competency models are needed. A competency model is a set of success factors, and includes the key behaviors required for excellent performance in a particular role[10].

To set the context for the theoretically derived competency classes, here's a quick overview of some classification patterns. Various models for the classification of abilities are presented in the literature. Most commonly, researchers define classifications based on their own theories and research objectives.

Katz and Kahn [11] grouped competency into three areas based on knowledge, attitude and skills of the employee,

which later expanded into the following four: 1) Technical or Functional expertise to perform the role 2) Managerial skills required to plan, organize, mobilize and utilize various resources 3) Human ability to motivate, utilize and develop human resources and 4) Conceptual abilities to visualize the invisible, think at abstract levels and use the thinking to plan future business.

Carrol and McCrackin grouped abilities into three main categories. The one is core competencies which is the basis of strategic direction [12]. It represents behavioral elements for all employees, such as the 'results/quality oriented. The second important is leadership/managerial competencies includes competencies related to leading organizations and people "visionary leadership," "strategic thinking," and "talent development. "The third categorized as functional competencies of job-specific skills required to perform a particular job or occupation [13].

G. Workforce Agility

The agility concepts can be just as easily applied to various business functions [14]. The term agility 'quickly widened to emerge as a broader business idea from which sprung others such as agile business relationships. Workforce agility has come to be understood an aspect of organizational agility [15]. It could be in reality viewed as the spine of organizational agility [16]. A single definition of workforce agility has not been shaped yet in the few research that have been carried out about it. It has been described from two perspectives: the ability standpoint and the capability perspective. Those who have defined it from the capability perspective emphasize people as having the capability no longer only to respond to change in a well-timed manner however additionally to take advantage of its rewards.

Workforce agility as a capability is derived from Dyer & Shafer 's framework used for the classification of workforce agility behaviors and attributes [17]. It contains three dimensions specifically proactivity, adaptability, and generative behavior. Proactivity is in addition subdivided into initiation and improvisation. Workers are proactive when they search for and courageously pursue opportunities that will possibly lead to the success of the organization [18]. The workforce is agile when it shows proactiveness in form of improvising when unforeseen situations occur using their knowledge to arrive at the best result for the firm. The proactive dimension of workforce agility as the situation in which a person initiates programs or processes that impact the changing environment positively [16].

The adaptivity entails changing oneself in order to better fit a new environment [19]. This requires for interpersonal and cultural adaptability [16]. Professional flexibility is also warranted by adaptable behavior. Professional flexibility is the ability to take on a variety of duties and quickly switch roles within teams or tasks. Resilience is asserted to be a further feature of the workforce agility behavior [18]. Positive attitudes toward novel concepts, technology, and other changes, like process modifications, tolerance of unexpected situations, differing of opposing viewpoints, and coping with difficult conditions, are signs of resilience. Continuous skill development and participation in

knowledge-sharing and information-gathering activities are two aspects of generative behavior [17].

H. Conceptual Framework for Behavioral Competencies and Workforce Agility

The framework for the empirical investigation is built using the review studies that have been discussed. The conceptual structure shown in figure 5 is based on the theoretical concepts of behavioral competencies of workforce agility. The conceptual framework summarizes the ideas covered in this study and acts as a roadmap for the research's subsequent phases, which aim to provide a more comprehensive knowledge of workforce agility.

Figure 1: Conceptual framework of the study

I. Hypothesis

Generic concerns about transferrable performance elements have led to the adoption of the discourse of behavioral competencies, defined as employee characteristics, rather than competence, which is presumptively also accompanied by more context-specific knowledge and skill. Furthermore, the following constructs of motivation, commitment, analytical reasoning, foresight, leadership, emotional stability, communicational skills are taken under behavioral perspective for this study. In Indian contextual understanding of agility dimensions of flexibility, adaptivity, developmental, collaborative, competent, speed and informative have chosen to build the frame work of this study. This proposed empirical investigation the hypothesis have framed with behavioral competencies and agility dimensional relationship. These are vital force to understand the performance of the workforce.

H1: Employee motivation is significantly and positively related to workforce agility

H2: Employee commitment is significantly and positively related to workforce agility

H3: Employee analytical reasoning is significantly and positively related to workforce agility

H4: Employee foresight is significantly and positively related to workforce agility

H5: Employee leadership is significantly and positively related to workforce agility

H6: Employee emotional stability significantly and positively related to workforce agility

H7: Employee communication significantly and positively related to workforce agility

II. METHODOLOGY

The scope of agility research is enormous and young filed to investigate. This study is focused on banking sector, very specifically ahead with the behavioral competencies with the agility effect of the employee. The research gap of variables is selected after proper reviewed of the available early studies.

This study is proposed to know the selective employee competencies influence on agility attributes concern with measurable key aspects that determines the opinion of the respondents. More over this study focused on to evolve the behavioral competency factors influencing the agility attributes of the banking employee. This investigation finds out the relationship of competencies and agility are covered: Motivation, Commitment, Analytical reasoning, Foresight, Leadership, Emotional stability, Communication skill and agility attributes of Flexibility, Adaptivity, Developmental, Collaborative, Competent, Speed, Informative.

Respondent opinion has collected through structured questionnaire. Secondary data is viewed through published papers; review and applicable journals etc. substantially to accent the conceptual analysis of competencies and agility relationship model. The sampling technique involved is convenient sampling. The data of the survey categorically confined to 298 Indian banking employees, in view Indian banking is more transformative with mergers, acquisitions and digital then ever at present economical and global context.

III. ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

The analysis of results is calculated with the SPSS descriptive and factor analysis to know the behavioral competencies of the employee influence on workforce agility attributes of the banking employees. To know the relationship of the variables correlation and regression analysis are tabulated. The questionnaire is constructed with the scale of five-point Likert scale. In a reliability check of consisting items of the questionnaire (fourteen items) Cronbach's Alpha calculated value is .704. It shows good reliability and consistency of the variables for further analysis.

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics

Scale Statistics			
Mean	Variance	Std. Deviation	N of Items
45.50	54.338	7.371	14
Variables		Mean	St. Deviation (N 298)
Motivation		3.24	1.171
Commitment		3.10	1.274
Analytical reasoning		3.53	.982
Foresight		3.45	1.041
Leadership		3.11	1.160
Emotional stability		3.51	1.229
Communication skill		3.16	1.205
Flexibility		3.19	1.192
Adaptability		3.24	1.206
Developmental		3.21	1.162
Collaborative		3.22	1.205
Competent		3.13	1.240
Speed		3.10	1.279
Informative		3.17	1.214

From the table 1 descriptive statistics of mean and standard deviation of 14 variables are calculated. Total mean of 45.50 and standard deviation 7.371 and variance 54.338 are observed of the variables. In a correlation coefficient analysis, the relationship between the employee behavioral competencies of motivation, commitment, analytical reasoning, foresight, leadership, emotional stability,

communication skill and work force agility attributes flexibility, adaptivity, developmental, collaborative, competent, speed and informative is have good positive and negative correlation and observed the significant relation (.000) among the variables. Pearson Correlation is significant at the 0.01**, 0.05* level (2-tailed). N 298

Table 2: Regression Analysis

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics				
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change
1	.687	.472	.460	.827	.472	37.073	7	290	.000

Table 2 represents human behavior of competencies tend to have adjusted R² values less than 50%. that is .460. The reason behind this is that predicting employee behavior is a more difficult task. From the table 2 drawn the essential conclusion independent variables of employee competencies of the model motivation, commitment, analytical reasoning, foresight, leadership, emotional stability, communication

skills have shown less influence on dependent variable workforce agility attributes of flexibility, adaptivity, developmental, collaborative, competent, speed and informative. It implies that 54% of other factors are playing significant role of influence on workforce agility. The Durbin Watson test statistic is 1.888 < 2 (lower than critical value) detected positive auto correlation in the residuals.

Table 3: ANOVA

ANOVA						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	177.563	7	25.366	37.073	.000
	Residual	198.423	290	.684		
	Total	375.987	297			
a. Dependent Variable: Workforce agility b. Predictors: (Constant), Motivation, Commitment, Analytical reasoning, Foresight, Leadership, Emotional stability, Communication skill						

In a table 3 an ANOVA was performed to compare the influence of behavioral competencies of (IV) on workforce

agility employee attributes (DV) implies there is a statistical significance (F value 37.073 and p-value is .000).

IV. FACTOR ANALYSIS

Table 4: KMO and Bartlett's Test

KMO and Bartlett's Test		
Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		.714
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	888.521
	df	91
	Sig.	.000

From the table 4 denotes the KMO value is respectable (0.714). also, Bartlett’s test rejects the null hypothesis that the variables aren’t related as the approximate chi-square value is 888.521 at 91 degrees of freedom which is significant at five percent level. The test provides probability

that the correlation matrix has significant correlations among at least some of the variables in a dataset, a prerequisite for factor analysis to work. thus, the factor analysis is considered as an applicable technique [20].

Table 5: Communalities

Communalities		
	Initial	Extraction
Goal oriented behavior	1.000	.646
Dedicated to a cause and activity	1.000	.360
Following a sequence of numbers	1.000	.363
The ability to predict the needed in the future	1.000	.553
Ability to inspire a team to achieve a certain goal	1.000	.751
Capacity to maintain balance in stress	1.000	.567
Able to communicate and understand effectively	1.000	.752
The ability to willingness to change	1.000	.461
The capacity to be modified for a new use or purpose	1.000	.771
State of achievements	1.000	.790
Work together in a joint intellectual effort	1.000	.581
Capable of performing the job effectively	1.000	.702
Multiple tasks completed in specified time	1.000	.532
Providing useful information	1.000	.612
Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.		

From the table 5 Communalities are calculated sum of square factor loadings. Generally, an item factor loading is recommended higher than 0.30 or 0.33 cut value. All fourteen factors are of employee competencies and agility factor values are recommended for the next level.

In a factor loadings employee behavioral competencies named as, ability to inspire a team to achieve a certain goal as a factor (F1) leadership (.751), employee ability to

communicate and understand effectively as a factor (F2) communication skill (.752) and workforce agility attributes of the capacity to be modified for a new use or purpose named the factor (F3) as a adaptability (.771), state of achievements as a factor (F4) as developmental (.790) and capable of performing the job effectively the skill stated as factor (F5) competent (.702) are observed from the extraction method (PCA) loadings.

Table 6: Total Variance Explained

Factor	Total Variance Explained								
	Initial Eigenvalues			Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings			Rotation Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	Variance % of	Cumulative %	Total	Variance % of	Cumulative %	Total	Variance % of	Cumulative %
F1	3.348	23.916	23.916	3.348	23.916	23.916	2.828	20.203	20.203
F2	1.612	11.515	35.432	1.612	11.515	35.432	1.557	11.119	31.322
F3	1.303	9.310	44.742	1.303	9.310	44.742	1.538	10.985	42.307
F4	1.166	8.326	53.068	1.166	8.326	53.068	1.373	9.805	52.112
F5	1.012	7.226	60.294	1.012	7.226	60.294	1.145	8.181	60.294

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

Table 6 leftmost section shows the variance explained by the initial result. Only five factors in the initial result have eigen values greater than 1. Together, they regard for nearly 60.294% of the variability in the original behavioral competency variables of leadership, communication skills, and workforce agility attributes of adaptability, developmental and competent of the employees. This suggests that five latent influences are associated with the operation, but there remains room for a lot of unexplained variation. The section of this table 6 shows the variance explained by the extracted factors before rotation. The cumulative variability explained by these five factors in the extracted

result is about 60%, a difference of 10% from the initial result. therefore, about 10% of the variation explained by the initial result is lost due to latent factors unique to the original variables and variability that simply cannot be explained by the factor model. The rightmost section of the above table shows the variance explained by the extracted factors after rotation. The rotated factor model makes some small adaptations to factor 1, but factor 2 to 5 is left nearly unchanged. Look for changes between the unrotated and rotated factor matrices to see how the rotation affects the interpretation of the first and other four factors. The rotation matrix gathered in seven iterations.

Table 7: Coefficients

Coefficients						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.002	.370		.006	.995
	Motivation	.496	.046	.539	10.875	.000
	Commitment	.171	.044	.192	3.908	.000
	Analytical reasoning	.147	.063	.105	2.325	.021
	Foresight	.148	.055	.125	2.688	.008
	Leadership	-.091	.065	-.069	-1.397	.164
	Emotional stability	-.022	.054	-.020	-.414	.679
	Communication skill	.063	.037	.076	1.714	.088

a. Dependent Variable: Workforce agility

V. DISCUSSION

Table 7 depicts that employee behavioral competencies are more influenced on workforce agility. In this study is to reveal that the motivated employee is highly committed and well-analytically reasoned have foresight to solve the problems and agile to do work more effectively in the organization. Hypothesis (H1: Motivation .000>.05, H2: Commitment.000>.05, H3: Analytical reasoning .021>.05, H4: Foresight 008>.05) are positively significant influence on agility attributes of adaptability, developmental and competent. Similarly, the result shows the competencies of employee leadership (H5), emotional stability (H6) and communication skills (H7) are not in positive direction to influence workforce agility. It also observed that behavioral competencies of motivation ($\beta = .539$), commitment ($\beta = .192$), were found to be strongly

associated with workforce agility attributes. The findings of this study conclude the focus on leadership, emotional stability and communication skills of the employee is a need of the concern to improve.

VI. MANAGERIAL IMPLICATIONS

Based on empirical understanding the following managerial implications are drawn under.

- The motivated employees are good at reasoning and have commitment and foresight towards the work to perform. These competencies relate with agility of adaptability prepared the employees for the new changes in internal and external system.
- The required skills of technical and managerial competent skills are essential to perform the job and achieve desired job results.

- In a banking to overcome the pressure emotional stability of an employee is highly essential to face challenges. Focus on emotional balanced behavior of the employee is flexible, adaptable and speedy in nature to respond situations.
- Manager's job is not only managing the people in routine tasks, they should be a leader to inspire the employees with an effective communication. Furnishing information in time help the employees work in team collaboration to share the tasks, and flexible schedules develop the competence in workforce.

VII. CONCLUSION

Retail banking services are demand oriented. The structured data and sensible information of knowledge is highly essential to carry forward the operations. The competencies of the employees are not only sufficient to perform the job. In a dynamic change of business, employees needed agile characteristics to take up the tasks more effectively. This empirical evidence supports to find out the relation of employee competencies of motivation, reasoned, commitment, foresight with adaptability, development and the competent agility is a strategic move to achieve desired outcome.

CONFLICTS OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest.

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